

D1.2: Open call documentation 2

*Documentation for the IMPETUS
Open Call for Funding 2024*

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Deliverable description

Text

Deliverable	D1.2, Open call documentation 2
Work Package	WP1
Due Date	31 st December 2023
Lead beneficiary of this deliverable	KCL
Version	1
Dissemination Level* PU / CO / CI	PU
Author(s) and Institution(s)	Gefion Thuermer (KCL)
Submission Date	14 th December 2023

Reviewers	María Anguiano (Zabala) Sara San Martín (Zabala)
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***PU**: Public / **CO**: Confidential Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) / **CI**: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Log of changes

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review.

Version	Date	Status	Author	Action
V0	29/11/2023	First full draft	Gefion Thuermer	Updated same deliverable from OC1 with new details
V1	13/12/2023	Review	María Anguiano Sara San Martín	Reviewed all documentation
V2	14/12/2023	Final version	Gefion Thuermer	Implemented reviewer comments

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101058677. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1. Summary

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the documentation for the second open call for funding in the IMPETUS project, which includes the following documents:

- Challenge Definitions
- Guide for Applicants
- Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)
- Application form
- Declaration of Honour
- Letter of Support template
- EasyChair user guide
- Call Announcement

These documents will be used for the open call, which will run from 10th January to 14th March 2024. Especially the FAQ will be continuously updated as we receive questions during the call period; all other documents will be revised at the end of the call period, in preparation for the third open call, schedule to run January through March 2025.

Please note that, while the timeline for the open call for funding is aligned with the call for nominations for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science, this document refers to the call for funding only.

2. Purpose and role in IMPETUS

This document was created primarily by KCL who will implement the open call for funding. The call documentation is largely an updated version of the same documents used successfully in the first open call, considering some learnings from the first implementation of the process, as outlined in D1.4, Open Call Summary 1.

2.1 Contribution towards project objectives

This deliverable is key to achieving milestone 4 of the project: Open Call 2, and contributes to the following objectives/key results: “Call challenges defined (including with citizen panel), relevant criteria and processes (i.e. evaluation) defined, and call and related documentation published.”

It includes all the documentation relevant to run the call, which will be in place on our project website by the time the call launches on 10th January 2024. In this second open call, we aim to reach 350 applications, and recruit 36 kickstarting and 10 sustaining citizen science initiatives. Results of the call will be summarised at the end of the selection period in D1.5 Open call summary report 2.

2.2 Relationship with other WPs

The Guide for applicants especially was developed in close alignment with all other WPs, and with extensive feedback from all consortium members and reviewers engaged in the process in the first round.

It includes a timeline of the negotiation and acceleration, as well as commitments of the participants during these periods, such as training and reporting requirements, which were discussed and aligned with WPs 2 (Accelerator), 4 (Policy), 5 (Impact) and 7 (Project Management).

We also decided to continue to align the timelines between the open calls for the accelerator, and nominations for the Prize, in order to maximise the effectiveness of outreach activities, and increase the number of applications for both areas. This has been highlighted in the documentation, and the funding call will remain open a few days longer than the Prize call, to prevent applicants applying for one call only due to the conflicting deadlines.

3. Challenge definition

The **first challenge** for the IMPETUS open call was defined by the consortium, based on the indicators for sustainable development goals and goals of the European Green Deal. The theme ***Citizen Science for Sustainable Lifestyles*** was set out in the Grant Agreement. Both goals

frameworks and indicators were revised to select the most appropriate elements which could be addressed through citizen science. In addition to the two focus SDGs (3 – Good Health and Wellbeing; 2 – Zero Hunger), the IMPETUS consortium decided to include SDG12 – Responsible Consumption and Production in this challenge, which was originally anticipated for the third open call. The next open call (in 2025) will focus more solidly on sustainability and climate, which are currently cross-cutting themes.

The **second challenge** was defined by the IMPETUS Citizen Panel. The panel was recruited from citizen science practitioners in October 2022, and defined the highly successful *Cities for Life* challenge for the first open call. The panel was expanded in September 2023 to include 20 members, which added ten and replaced three members who had dropped out.

The purpose of the citizen panel is threefold:

1. define challenges for the open accelerator call – the method we use to recruit citizen science initiatives that will receive funding and support;
2. contribute to the nomination and selection of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science; and
3. help spread the word about citizen science in Europe, and Impetus' mission.

The panel members are citizen science practitioners from across Europe, and consists of twenty members, who were selected based on a variety of criteria, including gender, expertise and geographical diversity. Individual member profiles are available on the IMPETUS website:

<https://impetus4cs.eu/about/citizen-panel/>.

The new panel first got together on the 6th October 2023, where they brainstormed to define a list of topics that they felt would be relevant for citizen science to address. This was then expanded through collaborative online tools (Google Docs and Miro board). The initial list included:

1. Misinformation
2. Cultural Heritage
3. Social inequality
4. Rural-urban divides
5. Mobility
6. Health
7. Oceans and water bodies
8. Countering pollution
9. Agriculture

- 10. Climate adaptation
- 11. AI

The panel discussed and ranked the different challenge options on 13th November and settled on *Justice and Equity* as the second challenge, with subtopics focusing on Health and Climate Adaptation. The challenge text was then developed by the panel with support from the consortium and revised by the panel in a meeting on 29th November. It was completed in a collaborative document on 6th December. It is provided in Annex 1. We will continue to work with the citizen panel, and plan to expand it by ten members every year.

The **third challenge** was added following discussions at the IMPETUS plenary in September 2023, where the consortium highlighted the need to enable more bottom-up projects to apply, as the selection criteria (e.g. having an existing community suggesting applications for Sustaining grants) seemed to provide them less opportunity than they deserved. It was thus decided to add an open challenge specifically for bottom-up projects, which would give excellent yet otherwise overlooked projects an opportunity to apply. In order to assess the eligibility of projects in this challenge, we decided that applicants in this challenge would need to provide a letter of support from the respective community, outlining their past and future involvement, as well as their anticipated benefits. A template for this purpose has also been developed and will be made available to applicants.

4. Changes from last open call

The key changes that were made to the documentation overall include:

- In the **Challenges**
 - o Updated topics in line with new SDGs to focus and citizen panel preferences, and added an open challenge for bottom-up projects (see above).
 - o Added a new eligibility criterion for the *Communities* challenge: We will assess eligibility of bottom-up projects through a letter of support from the community.
- In the **Guide for Applicants**
 - o Included more detailed guidance on eligibility, including clarification that projects who received a Kickstarting grant in the first open call *can* apply for a Sustaining grant in this open call (and vice versa).

- Included expectations and timeline of activities during the Accelerator, so projects can anticipate their schedule when applying.
- Changes the threshold for the shortlist to “up to 92 applications with the highest points, and no less than three points in each area.” This was necessary because the prior threshold (3+ points per area, 12+ points overall) resulted in too many applicants reaching the interview stage.
- In the **FAQ**
 - Highlighted that applications for Grant and Prize are possible and encouraged.
 - Removed some inconsistencies regarding data use and interview schedules.
- In the **Application Form**
 - Clarified the rules about what can and cannot be done with the form itself.
 - Reshuffled questions so that activities are no longer described across different sections.
- On **EasyChair submission platform**
 - Includes new questions to inform all the processes that build on this data, i.e. contract development, CSI onboarding into the Accelerator, impact assessment, and reporting across Funding and Prize call.
 - Created a detailed user guide for EasyChair, including clarification of notifications applicants will receive.

5. Open Call documentation

The relevant documents are available from our website, where they will also be made available to applicants during the call:

1. Challenge Definitions (see Annex 1)
2. Call Announcement (see Annex 2)
3. [Guide for Applicants](#)
4. [Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQ\)](#)
5. [EasyChair user guide](#)
6. [Application form](#)
7. [Letter of Support Template](#)
8. [Declaration of Honour](#)

6. Annex1 – Challenges

Challenge 1: Citizen Science for Sustainable Lifestyles

Why this matters

Citizen Science engages volunteers in a range of scientific activities. This helps educate and inform citizens in the subject matter and leads to a greater public understanding of how science and scientists work. Participation in Citizen Science can increase trust in science and expert opinions, enhance critical thinking, and ultimately fight misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Scientists can learn from Citizen Science about what people genuinely care about, the impact their work has or should have in society, and become more participatory, by involving volunteers early on in co-designing the research, collecting, cleaning, and analysing the data, documenting the results, and sharing the recognition. Citizen Science is playing an ever more important role in how researchers and innovators engage with society, and how they contribute to common concerns. However, Citizen Science sometimes struggles to achieve recognition and impact because citizen and ‘professional’ science practices differ, and citizen scientists have a harder time gaining access to local stakeholders and policy makers. Results of Citizen Science are chronically underutilised, although we know that they can add value to virtually everything from meeting Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets to boosting social and environmental innovations, all while being closely aligned with local communities.

While Green Deal and SDG targets may seem abstract for many citizen scientists, their projects may already be working toward monitoring them, through activities such as environmental measurements (for example air, water or soil quality), or monitoring (for example insect or bird observations).

What we are looking for

In our Open Call 2024, IMPETUS is looking for Citizen Science projects that contribute to sustainable development goals related to the theme of “Sustainable Lifestyles”. Specifically, we are interested in projects that address one or more of the following topics, which are related to SDGs #2, #3 and #12:

- **Food:** Fair and sustainable food production; access to safe, nutritious, and sustainable food; cost of living
- **Mobility:** Active travel (e.g. walking, cycling) and sustainable transport; reducing pollution and improving air quality
- **Waste:** Use and management of natural resources; circularity and recycling; reduced consumption and waste

Applicants should contribute to at least one of these topics, and enable the monitoring of at least one [established indicator](#), by providing monitoring data, or directly contributing to their achievement at local, regional, or national level.

How we select projects

We particularly welcome applications from projects that are led by women or non-binary persons, and that are run by, or actively involve, underrepresented groups and their public representation. This includes those belonging to groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination, such as refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQ+ community, those with disabilities; or from [lower-middle income countries](#); as well as projects that focus on inclusion dimensions of their research.

All projects **will also be assessed against criteria of equality, diversity, equity, openness, and potential impact on policy.**

IMPETUS has an [inclusive view of Citizen Science](#) initiatives, which can have a wide-ranging scope of scientific and social activities that engage citizens and aim to deliver scientific advancement and social benefits, support communities, and foster an open and inclusive civil society.

Eligible projects could include but are not limited to:

- Citizen engaged in digital humanities research
- Initiatives that incorporate characteristics of Citizen Science as defined by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
 - Science and research communication with citizens
 - Participatory artistic-led research
 - Science education that engages citizens

What we offer

Successful applicants will receive funding and support to deliver a seven-month project. Support will include training and expert guidance from a range of experts within and beyond the IMPETUS consortium, as well as peer-to-peer support and exchange.

Projects can apply for two kinds of grants, depending on their current development stage:

- Projects that are no more than six months into their Citizen Science journey and are yet to establish a community and/or data collection and processing procedures, can apply for a **Kickstarting grant**, worth 20,000 €.
- Projects that are more advanced, with established processes, an engaged community, and initial evidence of impact, can apply for a **Sustaining grant**, worth 10,000 €. We expect these grants to be awarded for the continuation, enhancing of impact, and/or further establishment of existing projects.

The funds provided can be spent on personnel costs, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

Challenge 2: Citizen Science for Justice and Equity

Why this matters

Justice and Equity directly or indirectly affects us all: Gender, LGBTQIA+, regional and cultural backgrounds, skin colour and physical characteristics, and mental wellbeing can all contribute to inequities. All of these aspects are further influenced by persisting social inequalities, such as the rural-urban divide, economic and environmental fragility, disability, wealth, and many more. Rural communities especially are not only frequently underrepresented but also face specific challenges, such as depopulation, ageing, limited mobility and connectivity.

We focus on two related topics in this space where we believe citizen science can make a big difference: **Climate Resilience and Health**. Citizen science can contribute to these topics in many ways, such as mapping the impact of climate change on (vulnerable) people and the environment or monitoring and taking action on inequities in health care. Citizen science can also help make these topics more accessible to the public and help citizens not only understand them better but also engage in the development of solutions.

- **Climate Resilience:** Climate change related challenges affect almost everyone in every corner of Europe. We need to move from measuring climate impacts to adapting to the changes that are already occurring. Citizen science has already started this work and can be a vehicle to help citizens understand complex concepts such as pollution, biodiversity, or ecosystem solutions; only if they understand how these issues affect them and their communities are they in a position to contribute their views and be heard. We are looking for citizen science projects that focus on changing citizen behaviour, raising awareness of things individual citizens can do, and collectively affecting societies and moving them toward adaptation to the new climate situation and reducing vulnerabilities.
- **Health:** Health issues have an overarching impact in all areas of society, such as chronic diseases, the lasting effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, and social and economic determinants of health outcomes. Citizen science in this area often takes the form of data classification (e.g. Fold-It), trackers collecting and making citizen data available (e.g. AppleHealth, FitBit), and patient-led initiatives, often at small scale. There are many more areas where citizen science could contribute, especially related to patient experiences and equity and inequalities in health care provision and systems.

These two topics are also connected, for example, in areas such as environmental effects causing health crises and societal inequalities

affecting both citizens' health and their capacity to deal with the effects of climate change.

What we are looking for

This IMPETUS challenge calls for Citizen Science projects that have the capacity to help make European society more just and equitable. It will focus on two key challenges that can be addressed through Citizen Science:

1. **Climate resilience**, and ways to improve existing responses to the effects of climate change, including effects on vulnerable groups; and
2. **Health**, and inequalities in health, including what causes them (e.g. underlying social inequalities, COVID19) and promoting health through scientific research and health literacy.

Applicants should aim to implement projects that contribute to research that enables solutions to these issues. Projects that address topics in social and artistic research are explicitly included in this call.

How we select projects

We particularly welcome applications from projects that are led by women or non-binary persons, and that are run by, or actively involve, underrepresented groups and their public representation. This includes those belonging to groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination, such as refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQ+ community, those with disabilities; or from [lower-middle income countries](#); as well as projects that focus on inclusion dimensions of their research.

All projects **will also be assessed against criteria of equality, diversity, equity, openness, and potential impact on policy.**

IMPETUS has an [inclusive view of Citizen Science](#) initiatives, which can have a wide-ranging scope of scientific and social activities that engage citizens and aim to deliver scientific advancement and social benefits, support communities, and foster an open and inclusive civil society.

Eligible projects could include but are not limited to:

- Citizen engaged in digital humanities research
- Initiatives that incorporate characteristics of Citizen Science as defined by ECSA
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- Projects that are more advanced, with established processes, an engaged community, and initial evidence of impact, can apply for a **Sustaining grant**, worth 10,000 €. We expect these grants to be awarded for the continuation, enhancing of impact, and/or further establishment of existing projects.

The funds provided can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

Challenge 3: Citizen Science for and with Communities

Why this matters

Citizen Science engages volunteers in a range of scientific activities. This helps educate and inform citizens in the subject matter and leads to greater public understanding of how science and scientists work. Participation in Citizen Science can increase trust in science and expert opinions, enhance critical thinking, and ultimately fight misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Scientists can learn from Citizen Science about what people genuinely care about, the impact their work has or should have in society, and become more participatory, by involving volunteers early on in co-designing the research, collecting, cleaning, and analysing the data, documenting the results, and sharing the recognition.

Citizen Science is playing an ever more important role in how researchers and innovators engage with society, and how they contribute to common concerns. However, Citizen Science sometimes struggles to achieve recognition and impact because citizen and 'professional' science practices differ, and citizen scientists have a harder time gaining access to local stakeholders and policy makers. Results of Citizen Science are chronically underutilised, although we know that they can add value to virtually everything from meeting Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets to boosting social and environmental innovations, all while being closely aligned with local communities.

While Green Deal and SDG targets may seem abstract for many citizen scientists, their projects may already be working toward monitoring them, through activities such as environmental measurements (for example air, water or soil quality), or monitoring (for example insect or bird observations).

What we are looking for

IMPETUS especially wants to support citizen science initiatives that are developed by and for communities. In this challenge, we invite applications on *any* topic, which are **developed and led by citizen scientists in a 'bottom-up' fashion**. Only projects **with evidenced support from their community** are eligible to apply. Applicants need to provide a letter of support from community members, explaining how the project was designed, will be implemented by, and ultimately benefit the communities of citizen scientists.

We will only fund up to five projects under this challenge; please be aware that your project should be **truly exceptional** to be considered for funding.

How we select projects

We particularly welcome applications from projects that are led by women or non-binary persons, and that are run by, or actively involve, underrepresented groups and their public representation. This includes

those belonging to groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination, such as refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQ+ community, those with disabilities; or from [lower-middle income countries](#); as well as projects that focus on inclusion dimensions of their research.

All projects **will also be assessed against criteria of equality, diversity, equity, openness, and potential impact on policy.**

IMPETUS has an [inclusive view of Citizen Science](#) initiatives, which can have a wide-ranging scope of scientific and social activities that engage citizens and aim to deliver scientific advancement and social benefits, support communities, and foster an open and inclusive civil society.

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What we offer

Successful applicants will receive funding and support to deliver a seven-month project. Support will include training and expert guidance from a range of experts within and beyond the IMPETUS consortium, as well as peer-to-peer support and exchange.

Projects can apply for two kinds of grants, depending on their current development stage:

- Projects that are no more than six months into their Citizen Science journey and are yet to establish a community and/or data collection and processing procedures, can apply for a **Kickstarting grant**, worth 20,000 €.
- Projects that are more advanced, with established processes, an engaged community, and initial evidence of impact, can apply for a **Sustaining grant**, worth 10,000 €. We expect these grants to be awarded for the continuation, enhancing of impact, and/or further establishment of existing projects.

The funds provided can be spent on personnel costs, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

7. Annex 2 – Call Announcement

TEMPLATE for FP7 Competitive Calls and H2020 Financial Support to Third Parties

To publish a call on the Funding & Tenders Portal (F&TP), the Project Officer must send to the F&TP team at least the following information:

	Information to be provided by the project consortium
Call title:	IMPETUS Citizen Science Challenge 2024
Full name of the EU funded project:	IMPETUS
Project acronym:	IMPETUS
Grant agreement number:	101058677
Call opening date:	10/01/2024 at 12:00 (Brussels time)
Call deadline:	14/03/2024 at 23:59 (Brussels time)
Expected duration of participation:	Participation for successful applicants will last 7 months
Total EU funding available:	Approximately 920,000 EUR Funding for kickstarting projects: 20,000 EUR (41x) Funding for sustaining projects: 10,000 EUR (10x)
Submission & evaluation process:	<p>Submission process:</p> <p>Applications will be made in English, online via the following platform: https://easychair.org/my/conference?conf=impetus4cs</p> <p>Applications will consist of a short proposal presenting the idea, implementation, resources and impact, as well as administrative information and a declaration of honour. The short proposal should follow the template available in the IMPETUS 'guide for applicants' and must not exceed 4 pages.</p> <p>Evaluation process:</p> <p>The evaluation will be divided into the following stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Eligibility check: the funding is available to legal entities established in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon Europe grants. Every entity is allowed to participate in one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium.2. Proposal review: each proposal will be assessed against four criteria: idea, implementation, team and community, and impact.3. Applicants will be informed of the results and short-listed candidates will be invited to an online interview with an expert panel.

	See IMPETUS' 'guide for applicants' accessible from the submission platform for more details on the evaluation process: www.impetus4cs.eu/opencall
Further information:	opencall@IMPETUS4cs.eu
Task description:	<p>The IMPETUS Open Call is intended to support the implementation and sustainability of citizen science projects addressing the IMPETUS challenge. For this call we are inviting projects that focus on the themes of <i>Citizen Science for Sustainable Lifestyles</i>, <i>Citizen Science for Justice and Equity</i>, and <i>Citizen Science for and with Communities</i>.</p> <p>Successful applicants will be expected to design, implement and present the findings from a related citizen science projects over the course of seven months, and actively engage in the IMPETUS Accelerator, including mentoring, networking, and training sessions.</p> <p>Applications which engage citizens in scientific activities producing new results, which are of mutual benefit to citizen scientists and project administrators alike will be prioritised. We particularly encourage projects that address marginalised, disadvantaged or vulnerable groups to engage in citizen science and expect that where possible, projects funded through the IMPETUS open call should be openly accessible to all.</p>